

Digitising Devotion: Mapping the Network of Vernacular Prayer Books in the Late Medieval Low Countries

Irene Van Eldere and Peter Verhaar | DH Benelux 2024

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The PRAYER project

The Hague, National Library of the Netherlands (KB), 133 E 22, f. 67v.

Pages of Prayer: The Ecosystem of Vernacular Prayer Books in the Late Medieval Low Countries, c. 1380-1550

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Middle Dutch prayer books

- Geert Grote (1340-1384)
- Devotio Moderna

Prayer book (Holland, c. 1520), Leiden University Libraries, BPL 3055, f. 9r.

Geert Grote Huis: skull and reconstruction, © Jako van Gorsel / KokBoekencentrum Uitgevers.

□ Core texts:

- Calendar
- Hours of the Virgin
- Seven Penitential Psalms
- Office of the Dead
- Litany of the Saints
- Hours of the Holy Spirit (long and short)
- Hours of the Cross (long and short)
- Hours of Eternal Wisdom

Ghetiden, Delft: Jacob Jacobszoon van der Meer, July 1484. München, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, 4 Inc.c.a. 364.

Book of Hours (Holland, c. 1440),
Athenaeumbibliotheek Deventer,
2000 D 19 KL, f. 83v-84r.

Book of Hours (Holland), Leiden
University Libraries, LTK 300, f. 135v-
136v.

- C. 850 manuscripts and 45 editions (c. 150 copies)
- Objective: Better understanding of the function of Middle Dutch prayer books within late medieval and early sixteenth-century religious practice and society

Data sources

- *Bibliotheca Neerlandica Manuscripta* (BNM) and BNM-I
- J. Deschamps and H. Mulder, *Inventaris van de Middelnederlandse handschriften van de Koninklijke Bibliotheek van België*
- Incunabula Short Title Catalogue
- STCN
- *Gesamtkatalog der Wiegendrucke*

The screenshot shows the BNM-I website with a blue header containing the logo and navigation. Below the header, there are four colored buttons: 'Tekstdragers' (blue), 'Teksten' (purple), 'Literatuur' (green), and 'Lexicon' (orange). The main content area is divided into two columns: 'Voorheen BNM' and 'Nu BNM-I'. The 'Voorheen BNM' section describes the historical context of the BNM database, while the 'Nu BNM-I' section highlights the new features and search capabilities of the updated system.

Data Model

- Export from BNM-I in JSON
- OCR of Mulder & Deschamps
- Conversion and standardisation of all records
- Database implementation in Heurist

https://github.com/peterverhaar/leiden_prayer

Shared Transmission

Prayer to St. Margareth

Prayer to St. Martin

Prayer to Ten thousand Martyrs

Prayer to Mary (in front of an image of Mary)

Prayer to be recited after the H. Communion

Prayer to St. Jerome

Prayer to St. Augustine

Prayer to St. Agnes

Prayer to God the Heavenly Father

Prayer to be recited before the H. Communion

Seven Pater Nosters/ Passion exercise

Prayer to be recited before the H. Communion

Prayer to St. Anne

Prayer before Confession

Prayer to be recited during the H. Communion

Prayer to St. Francis

Prayer to be recited after the H. Communion

Three Invocations of Mary

Prayer to the Heart of Christ

Prayer to be recited during the H. Communion

Prayer to Jesus Christ

Prayer to St. Gregory

Prayer to St. Christopher

Litany of All Saints

Questions

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